

HIPPARCOS

Star Distribution Models

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Summary

This note gives some improved formulae for the star density as function of magnitude and galactic latitude, and for the frequency of physical companions (double stars).

Star Density

Let $N(B, b)$ be the average number of stars per square degree brighter than blue magnitude B and at galactic latitude b . The following approximation holds for all $B < 16$ and all b :

$$\begin{aligned} \lg N(B, b) = & -3.63 + 0.489B - 0.002B^2 - \\ & - (0.86 - 0.084B + 0.007B^2)(1.4|\sin b| - 0.4 \sin^2 b) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

This formula is based on Allen (Astrophysical Quantities, 1973, p. 243), but with scaling corrections to agree with actual star numbers in CSI (Turon Lacarrieu, 1980). CSI contains some 15-25 % more stars down to $B = 9$ than expected from Allen's table.

It can be noted that $\sin b$ in (1) can be computed for a star at ecliptical coordinates (λ, β) by the formula

$$\sin b = \sin 30^\circ \sin \beta + \cos 30^\circ \cos \beta \cos(\lambda - 180^\circ) \quad (2)$$

since the north galactic pole is close to $\lambda = 180^\circ$, $\beta = 30^\circ$.

Let $\bar{N}(B)$ be the sky-averaged density of stars (deg^{-2}) down to blue magnitude B . From (1), the following approximation is derived ($B < 16$):

$$\lg \bar{N}(B) = -4.06 + 0.525B - 0.005B^2 \quad (3)$$

Star Colours

The average star colour around B = 10 is $\overline{B-V} = 0.7$. The distribution is roughly as follows:

B-V	frequency
-0.3 to 0.0	5 %
0.0 to 0.5	40 %
0.5 to 1.0	20 %
1.0 to 1.5	30 %
1.5 to 2.0	5 %

Double Stars

Let $P(r, h)$ be the probability of finding a physical companion to a given star with separation (ρ) and magnitude difference (Δm) satisfying $\rho > r$ and $\Delta m < h$ (by definition, $\Delta m \geq 0$, since the companion is the fainter component). From statistics of known double stars around B = 9 (brighter component) and with $0.2'' < \rho < 12''$, the following law was derived after correcting for the assumed incompleteness of the material:

Pr(companion with $\rho > r$ and $\Delta m < h$) $\equiv$

$$\equiv P(r, h) = (r/0.002'')^{-0.33} [1 - (1 - h/13)^2] \quad (4)$$

Since (4) provides a reasonable extrapolation for $\rho > 12''$, it should be useful for all $\rho > 0.2''$.